

The peculiarities of small genre in the works of Katherine Mansfield.

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This paper explores the unique and impactful use of the "small genre" in the works of Katherine Mansfield. Examining her short stories, sketches, and vignettes, the presentation analyzes how Mansfield employed this form to create powerful microcosms of human experience. Katherine Mansfield, a prominent modernist writer, often explored women's issues in her works, offering valuable insight into the social and cultural dynamics of her time. Her writings, particularly her short stories, provide rich material for examining gender roles, societal expectations, and the experiences of women.

We will consider how Mansfield's focus on seemingly insignificant moments, everyday interactions, and subtle nuances of emotion allows her to illuminate the complexities of human relationships, societal expectations, and the fragility of life itself. The paper will explore how Mansfield's masterful manipulation of narrative structure, characterization, and evocative language transforms these small, seemingly mundane moments into profound and poignant explorations of the human condition. The presentation will further examine how Mansfield's work challenges traditional notions of genre and provides valuable insights into the enduring power and impact of her literary legacy.

Even as more recent assessments of modernism have taken the contributions of women more seriously, the fact that Mansfield's preferred genre was short fiction seems to have made it easier to dismiss her role and influence in favor of her peers who wrote novels, a genre that remains the general measure of success in the literary world.³

By delving into specific examples from her most celebrated works, this presentation aims to demonstrate how Mansfield's mastery of the "small genre" transcends mere brevity. Through her sharp observations and meticulous crafting of detail, she reveals a universe of

³ Martin, W. Todd. "Katherine Mansfield Among the Moderns." *South Atlantic Review*, vol. 80, no. 1–2, 2015, pp. 178–90. *JSTOR*, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/soutatlarevi.80.1-2.178>. Accessed 4 Feb. 2024.

emotion, thought, and experience within the confines of a seemingly simple story. **Katherine Mansfield's preference for the short story reflects two key trends.** At the turn of XX century, the genre system of English prose was undergoing a transformation. The short story was gaining prominence, emerging as an equal partner to the novel in the literary world. Another crucial factor influencing Mansfield's choice was the specific social consciousness of the era. She possessed a keen ability to anticipate the emerging trends of XX century literature, which placed greater emphasis on capturing the collective social experience of a particular time period. Similar to Anton Chekhov, Mansfield wasn't as interested in individual characters as she was in reflecting the broader "states of a single epochal consciousness." For this purpose, the short story format proved to be the ideal medium.⁴

Katherine Mansfield's prose departs from traditional styles in several ways. Her writing avoids overly flowery metaphors and hidden symbolism. She pays close attention to detail, but these details are not necessarily the most obvious or typical. Instead, she focuses on seemingly insignificant or incidental details. The richness of these details replaces the need for elaborate poetic imagery. The core of Mansfield's stories lies in the characters' inner struggles. External plot points (fabula) take a backseat to the exploration of the characters' internal experiences. Mansfield doesn't reveal a character's psychology through grand actions. Instead, she uses seemingly minor, everyday details that subtly hint at the character's experiences. This approach emphasizes the importance of subtext in Mansfield's characterization.

This exploration will offer a fresh perspective on Mansfield's work, highlighting her skill in conveying universal truths through seemingly insignificant details and her ability to craft narratives that resonate deeply with readers long after the final word is read.

⁴ <https://www.dissercat.com/content/osobennosti-malogo-zhanra-v-tvorchestve-ketrin-mensfield>